

ISSN-NO.-2231-4687
IMPACT FACTOR-1.52

International Journal of Management and Economics

Vol. I

No. 12

November

2014

CHETAN PUBLICATIONS, AURANGABAD

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Indian Organized Retailing: Challenges and opportunities

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Introduction:

The retail sector is the backbone of any economy, determining its growth trajectory in a big way. India is Asia's largest retail market after China and Japan and retail is one of the largest employers in India. There is hectic activity in the sector in terms of expansion, entry of international brands and retailers, as well as focus on technology, operations and processes. All these present a tremendous opportunity in this new high growth industry.

Retailing in India is slightly different from that of the developed nations. It is divided into organized and unorganized sectors. Organized retail is described as the one where trading is taking place under a license or through the people who are registered under sales tax or income tax. On the other hand, the unorganized sector in India is more traditional in style which includes the local mom and pop stores (*kirana stores*), owner managed general stores, paan/beedi shops, convenience stores, hand carts and street vendors.

According to a study carried out by A.T. Kearney on global retailing trends in the world, it is found that India is least saturated and least competitive of all major global economies. A.T. Kearney prepares a Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) annually, in which it ranks the top 30 emerging economies for retail development and identifies the opportunities presented by these countries for the global retailers. In the 2011 GRDI tabulation, India ranks as the fourth hottest market for retail development, leaving behind china. India remains a tough place to do business, but it still has attractive demographics. India has a bumpy road to drive over the next few years. The long-term fundamentals remain strong: in particular, a large, young, increasingly brand- and fashion-conscious population. Retail growth of 14 to 15 percent per year is expected through 2015. Organized retail remains limited (7 percent in 2012), but it is expected to grow as the country urbanizes and retailers make new investments.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the emerging retail trends in India.
2. To critically examine the growth of organized retail sector in India.
3. To study the challenges faced by the organized retail sector in India.
4. To present the future prospects of organized retail sector in India.

Research Methodology

The present study is based on secondary data. The data and the information needed for the study is gathered from research publications, case studies, presentations, e-books, insights and reports of India Brand Equity Foundation (IBEF), a trust established by Department of Commerce, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India, Deloitte, Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP), IBSCDC (Asia Pacific's largest repository of Management Case Studies), Global Retail Development Index (GRDI), Competition Commission of India, etc.

Indian Retailing Scenario:

India is the 5th largest retail market in the world. The country ranks fourth among the surveyed 30 countries in terms of global retail development. The current market size of Indian retail industry is about US\$ 500 bn (Source: IBEF) and is expected to grow at the rate of 15-20% p.a. The retail industry is expected to increase to US\$ 750-850 billion by 2015 (according to a report by Deloitte). Retailing has played a major role all over the world in increasing productivity across a wide range of consumer goods and services. In the developed countries, the organized retail industry accounts for almost 80% of the total retail trade. In contrast, in India organized retail trade accounts for merely 8-10% of the total retail trade. * This highlights a lot of scope for further penetration of organized retail in India.

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Market Size:

India's retail market is expected to touch a whopping Rs 47 trillion (US\$ 782.23 billion) by 2016-17, expanding at a compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) of 15 per cent, according to a study by a leading industrial body. The total organised retail supply in 2013 stood at approximately 4.7 million square feet (sq ft), witnessing a strong year-on-year (y-o-y) growth of about 78 per cent over the total mall supply of 2.5 million sq ft in 2012. The foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows in single-brand retail trading during the period April 2000-January 2014 stood at US\$ 98.66 million, as per data released by Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP).

Fig.1 shows by 2012, the total market size reached US\$ 518 billion, thereby registering a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 7 per cent since 1998.

Source: IBEF

Market Breakup:

The sector can be broadly divided into two segments: Value retailing, which is typically a low margin - high volume business (primarily food and groceries) and Lifestyle retailing, a high margin-low volume business (apparel, footwear, etc). The sector is further divided into various categories, depending on the types of products offered. Food dominates market consumption with 60% share followed by fashion. The relatively low contribution of other categories indicates opportunity for organized retail growth in these segments, especially with India being one of the world's youngest markets. In 2012, Food and Grocery accounted for nearly 60 per cent of total revenues in the retail sector as shown in the below figure.

Figure-2

Source: IBEF

Break-up of all mall space by format in India:

Hypermarkets would be the largest retail segment, accounting for 21 per cent of total retail space by 2013-14 as shown in the below figure.

Figure-3

Source: IBEF

Organized Retailing in India:

Indian organized retail sector is in a nascent stage, with a few major players, compared to the 15 million kirana stores through which more than 90% of retailing happens in India. However, with the middle class Indian population and disposable income of the young population increasing, organized retailers were almost on the verge of a major breakthrough. New players are entering the retail sector with different formats and incumbents are continuously experimenting to attract customers. But understanding the Indian customer remains a tough task as many of the retailers have failed to establish their formats and many are only moderately successful (IBSCDC, 2009).

Organized retailing in India is witnessing a radical transformation. The increase in the number of retail chains across the country is an indication that organized retailing is emerging as an industry and will boom in a big way in the near future. Retailing like any product does follow a life cycle. India is currently at a stage where customers needed variety in products and retail formats (Srivastava, 2008). The change of attitudes of Indian consumers and the emergence of organized retail formats have transformed the face of retailing in India. Organized retailing offers huge potential for future growth of retailing in India (Kusuma et al.). Organized retailing comprises mainly of modern retailing with busy shopping malls, multi stored malls and huge complexes that offer a large variety of products in terms of quality, value for money and makes shopping a memorable experience. The retail sector is presently undergoing a transition in India. Previously, customers used to go to kirana Stores to purchases their necessities. This later changed to bigger shops run by one man with a few employees. Here all the work was done manually. Gradually more sophistication seeped into this sector and department stores came into being. Beginning in the mid-1990s, however, there was an explosion of shopping malls and plazas where customers interacted with professional and not with just one single person, the owner. An important point here is that customers' requirements are catered to by trained staff. Today, organized retailing has become an experience characterized by comfort, style and speed. It is something that offers a customer more control, convenience and choice along with an experience. Organized retailing is on continuous increase of its market share from the past. Retailing can be categorized as of different sectors like food and grocery, clothing and textiles, consumer durables, footwear, furniture and furnishing, catering services, jewellery and watches, books, music and gifts, mobile handsets and others. (Akhter and Eqbal, 2012).

Organized retailing is not threat to independent Mom and Pop stores as most of the consumers said that they never stopped visiting Kirana stores. They strongly agreed on coexistence of both is requirement of the day. Their frequency of going to kirana stores is reduced but it's kind of opportunities for reorienting Mom and Pop stores for attracting more customers. So, organized retailing is beneficial for India because it's not alarming to create conflict with unorganized stores but reshaping unorganized stores into budding/nascent organized stores. Modern retailing has miles to go in India. The growth of modern formats has been much slower in India as compared to other countries and the development of this sector is restricted by the presence of regulatory and structural constraints. (Manocha and Pandey, 2012).

Due to rapid urbanization and changing patterns of consumer taste and preferences, there is huge need for the organized retailing in India which offers unparalleled opportunities to the entrepreneurs and existing

businesses seeking an entry in retailing. A healthy competition would increase the quality of service of the existing local retailers and greater customer satisfaction in Indian society. As the Indian retail industry is getting organized day by day, there is no doubt that the retail scene will shine in coming days (Jayakumar and Geetha).

Availability of a wide range of brands from luxury goods to basic private label products gave consumers more options to choose from and also boosted awareness of particular brands and products. Domestic brands and local companies remained dominant among the players operating in retailing in India during 2014. In spite of various relaxations made to the rules regarding foreign direct investment in India, international companies remain cautious about India (CII Report, 2014).

Retail Formats in India:

- **Hyper Marts/ Super Markets:** large self – servicing outlets offering products from a variety of categories. Examples like Spencer’s, Big Bazaar.
- **Mom-and –pop Stores:** they are family owned business catering to small sections; they are individually handled retail outlets and have a personal touch.
- **Departmental Stores:** are general retail merchandisers offering quality products and services. Examples like Ebony, Shopper’s Stop, Westside.
- **Convenience Stores:** are located in residential areas with slightly higher prices goods due to the convenience offered. Examples like in & Out, Safal, 6ten.
- **Shopping Malls:** the biggest form of retail in India, malls offers customers a mix of all types of products and services including entertainment and food under a single roof.
- **E-trailers:** are retailers providing online buying and selling of products and services.
- **Discount Stores:** these are factory outlets that give discount on the MRP. Examples like Koutons, Nike, and Levis.
- **Vending:** it is a relatively new entry in the retail sector. Here beverages, snacks and other small items can be bought via vending machines.
- **Category Killers:** small specialty stores that offers a variety of categories. They are known as category killers as they focus on specific categories, such as electronics and sporting goods. This is also known as Multi Brand Outlets MBO’s.
- **Specialty Stores:** are retail chains dealing in specific categories and provide deep assortment. Mumbai’s Crossword Book Store and RPG’s Music World is a couple of examples. (Sunita Sikri, Ms. Dipti Wadhwa). 8%

Table: 1
Major Players in Indian Organized Retailing:

Major	Store Brands (Products)
Tata Group	Landmark (Books and music), Croma (Multi Brand Electronics), World of titan (Watches), Tanishq (Jewellery), Titan Eye+
Future Groups	Central (shopping mall), Big Bazaar (Hyper Market), Pantaloons (fashion outlet), Blue Sky (Sun glasses), Brand Factory (Multi Brand readymade Garments), KB’s Fair Price (Essential Products), Navaras (Jewellery), Planet Stores (Multi brand sports and life style specialty retail), aLL (fashion

Reliance Group	Reliance Fresh (neighborhood store), Reliance Mart (super market), Reliance super(mini mart), Reliance digital (Consumer durables and information technology), Reliance Trends (Apparel and accessories), Reliance wellness (health,
RPG Group	Spencer's (multi-format retail store), Music world (music and home video store) and Books & Beyond (Book Store)
K Raheja Group	Shoppers Stop (Clothing, accessories, fragrances, cosmetics, footwear and home furnishing store), Crossword (book store), In orbit Mall (Fashion, life style, food and

Source: IBEF

Government Initiatives:

The Government of India has allowed 100 per cent FDI in Single-Brand Retail Trading (SBRT) and has allowed 51 per cent FDI in Multi-Brand Retail Trading (MBRT). Just recently, the Competition Commission of India (CCI) approved the proposal of Tesco buying 50 per cent equity in Trent, which is the first-ever FDI proposal in multi-brand retail trade. According to the extant policy, foreign retailers investing more than 51 per cent can open outlets across the country on the condition that 30 per cent of their sourced sales would come from small to medium-sized domestic enterprises. Further, global chains will now need to invest only 50 per cent of the initial compulsory investment of US\$ 100 million in setting up cold storages and warehouses in India. The Confederation of All India Traders (CAIT) has signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with eBay to train domestic retailers to use the online market space as an additional tool for expanding their business. The agreement will enable Indian traders to export via eBay to 201 countries and sell at 4,306 Indian locations.

Reasons for the growth of retail industry in India:

Retail Industry, is one of the fastest changing and vibrant industries that, has contributed to the economic growth of our country. Within a very short span of time, Indian retail industry has become the most attractive, emerging retail market in the world. Healthy economic growth, changing demographic profile, increasing disposable income, changing consumer tastes and preferences are some of the key factors that are driving growth in the organised retail market in India.

Some of the factors responsible for the growth of organised retailing are as under:

1. Growth of middle class consumers:

In India the number of middle class consumer is growing rapidly. Rising consumer demand and greater disposable income has given opportunity for retail industry to grow and prosper. They expect quality products at decent prices. Modern retailers offer a wide range of products and value added services to the customers. Hence this has resulted into growth of organised retailing in India.

2. Increase in the number of working women:

Today the urban women are literate and qualified. They have to maintain a balance between home and work. The purchasing habit of the working women is different from the home maker. They do not have sufficient time for leisure and expect everything under one roof. They prefer one-stop shopping. Modern retail outlets therefore offer one store retailing.

3. Value for money:

Organised retail deals in high volume and are able to enjoy economies of large scale production and distribution. They eliminate intermediaries in distribution channel. Organised retailers offer quality products at reasonable prices. Example: Big Bazaar. Opportunity for profit attracts more and more new business groups for entering in to this sector.

4. Emerging rural market:

Today the rural market in India is facing stiff competition in retail sector also. The rural market in India is fast emerging as the rural consumers are becoming quality conscious. Thus due to huge potential in rural retailing organised retailers are developing new products and strategies to satisfy and serve rural customers. In India, Retail industry is proving the country's largest source of employment after agriculture, which has the deepest penetration into rural India.

5. Entry of corporate sector:

Large business tycoons such as Tata's, Birla's, and Reliance etc. have entered the retail sector. They are in a position to provide quality products and entertainment. As the corporate – the Piramals, the Tatas, the Rahejas, ITC, S.Kumar's, RPG Enterprises, and mega retailers- Crosswords, Shopper's Stop, and Pantaloons race to revolutionize the retailing sector.

6. Entry of foreign retailers:

Indian retail sector is catching the interest of foreign retailers. Due to liberalisation multinationals have entered out country through joint ventures and franchising. This further is responsible for boosting organised retailing.

7. Technological impact:

Technology is one of the dynamic factors responsible for the growth of organised retailing. Introduction of computerization, electronic media and marketing information system have changed the face of retailing. One of the major technological innovations in organised retailing has been the introduction of Bar Codes. With the increasing use of technology and innovation retailers are selling their products online with the help of Internet.

8. Rise in income:

Increase in the literacy level has resulted into growth of income among the population. Such growth has taken place not only in the cities but also in towns and remote areas. As a result the increase in income has led to increase in demand for better quality consumer goods. Rising income levels and education have contributed to the evolution of new retail structure. Today, people are willing to try new things and look different, which has increased spending habits among consumer.

9. Media explosion:

There has been an explosion in media due to satellite television and internet. Indian consumers are exposed to the lifestyle of various countries. Their expectations for quality products have risen and they are demanding more choice and money value services and conveniences.

10. Rise of consumerism:

With the emergence of consumerism, the retailer faces a more knowledgeable and demanding consumer. As the business exist to satisfy consumer needs, the growing consumer expectation has forced the retail organizations to change their format of retail trade. Consumer demand, convenience, comfort, time, location etc. are the important factors for the growth of organised retailing in India.

11. Urbanisation:

The Indian urban population is projected to increase from 28% to 40% of the total population by 2020 and incomes are simultaneously expected to grow in these segment. Increased urbanisation has led to higher customer density areas thus enabling retailers to use lesser number of stores to target the same number of customers. Aggregation of demand that occurs due to urbanization helps a retailer in reaping the economies of scale.

12. Demographics:

More than 50% of the population is less than 25 years of age and strong growth is expected to continue in this age bracket.

Challenges to the growth of organized retailing:

Organized retail in India is little over a decade old. It is largely an urban phenomenon and the pace of growth is still slow. Some of the reasons for this slow growth are:

1. Shortage of talented professionals:

The industry is facing a severe shortage of talented professionals, especially at the middle- management level. Areas gradually becoming critical are technology, supply chain, business development, marketing, product development and research. Successful Indian retailers are creating a robust second and third level of management by hiring aggressively for these key roles.

2. Logistical challenges:

Constant changes in consumer preferences and patterns, crowded marketplaces, efficient customer responsiveness and swiftly evolving retail formats are the hallmarks of today's retail environment in India. These factors pose a huge challenge for that all-important key to pushing growth in this kind of an environment - is an efficient and adaptable supply chain.

3. Fraud in retail is expensive:

Fraud and theft, including employee pilferage, shoplifting, vendor frauds and inaccuracy in supervision and administration costs the Indian retail industry about Rs 550-600 crores (USD 0.12-0.13 billion) every year.

4. The Kiranas continue:

The very first challenge facing the organized retail industry in India is competition from the unorganized sector. Traditionally retailing has established in India for centuries. It is a low cost structure, mostly owner operated, has negligible real estate and labour costs and little or no taxes to pay. Customer familiarity that runs from generation to generation is one big advantage for the unorganized sector. On the other hand, organized sector have big expenses to meet and yet have to keep prices low enough to compete with the traditional sector.

5. Lack of recognition as an industry:

Retail is not yet recognised as an industry in India. People are still reluctant to invest in retail sector. This hampers the development and availability of finance to the existing and new business players. India, it still faces substantial hurdles that will retard and inhibit its growth in the future. One of the key impediments is the lack of FDI status. This has largely limited capital investments in supply chain infrastructure.

6. High cost of real estate:

There has been a constant increase in real estate prices. Hence, the retail place is available at high lease rentals which reduce the profit earning capacity of the retailers.

7. Lack of adequate infrastructure:

The infrastructure facilities are not yet developed in India. India still continues to suffer from lack of basic infrastructure. Poor road, lack of warehousing facilities, power shortage, difficulties in communication etc. hampers the development of retail industry. Absence of infrastructure also characterised by high costs of transactions hampers the acceleration of organised retail sector in India.

8. Complex taxation system:

The sales tax rates vary from state to state. Organised retailers have to face multiple tax system. In last few years taxation system in India is subject to significant reforms. Due to this it becomes expensive to transfer the goods from one store to another. This has resulted into slow growth of organised retailing.

9. Restrictions on foreign direct investment (FDI):

FDI is not permitted in pure retail. Global retailers can enter in India only by way of franchise or joint ventures. This has restricted the growth of retail in India. FDI had positive results on the economy leading to greater efficiency and global integration. But restriction of pure FDI has again become the factor responsible for slow growth of organised retailing in India.

10. Huge geographical and regional differences:

India is a vast country. The population is also largely scattered. There exists huge diversity. Location is the most important factor determining the success of a retail store or a chain. Hence, it becomes difficult for retailer to cater to the needs of such diverse population.

11. Diversion of funds to the other sector:

Retailing in the initial period was not given prominence. The resources were diverted to the other sectors like banking, insurance, communication, transportation etc. This has resulted in slow growth of organised retailing in India.

Suggestions to overcome the challenges:

1. Acceptance of Industry Status to Retail: Industry status should be given to improve retail development, to facilitate organized financing and to establish insurance norms.

2. Incentives for Investments: Tax holiday norms for cold storage chains, infrastructure and investment in supply chain should be enacted.

3. Comprehensive Legislation: comprehensive legislation should be drafted and enacted with futuristic approach.

Road Ahead:

India remains a largely untapped and unorganized retail market, with several international retail companies yet to commence operations in the country. India holds a substantial advantage over other emerging retail destinations owing to its strong domestic consumption and low rate of market penetration by overseas retailers. India's new middle class is increasingly becoming brand conscious and willing to spend on quality goods, a trend which is creating numerous business opportunities for mid-range international brands. With political and economic sentiments already showing signs of improvement, we believe this is the right time for international retailers to look at India for expansion into the region. E-commerce is also expected to be the next major area for retail growth in India.

Conclusion:

India remains an appealing long-term retail destination for several reasons, starting with its demographics - a population of 1.2 billion people, half of whom are younger than 30 and roughly one-third of whom live in cities. Indians' disposable incomes are increasing, allowing them to spend more and try new products, brands, and categories while spending a lower proportion on food. Concerns for the industry include an opaque real estate market with high prices and low availability, high borrowing costs, personnel shortages, expensive supply chains, and unpredictable politics both locally and regionally. Thus retailers should focus on improving operations and back-end processes to increase profitability and growth. Furthermore, the recent national election of the Bharatiya Janata Party, which has promised more pro-business policies, many experts are feeling positive about India's long-term GDP outlook and industry growth.

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